

Assessment of Solar PV Potential on Facades: Toward Zero-Energy Buildings

Azizkhani M^{*1} and Grebby S^{†2}

¹Independent Researcher

²Nottingham Geospatial Institute, Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, NG7 2TU, UK

February 11, 2021

Summary

Solar photovoltaic (PV) energy is the most commonly used renewable energy source in urban areas. During the last decade, solar cell manufacturing costs have decreased significantly, alongside becoming more efficient. Furthermore, Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) provide a new opportunity for utilising solar energy via facades. Previous studies were unable to model the facades accurately, thus limiting assessments of the solar energy potential. This study aims to address this issue by assessing the feasibility of using BIPV on facades with the aid of 3D models. The results suggest that BIPV could play a critical role for zero-energy buildings in the near future.

KEYWORDS: Solar Potential, 3D Models, Photovoltaic, Facades, Zero-Energy Buildings

1. Introduction

Zero-energy building is one of the essential elements of smart cities. Several methods for reducing the building energy consumption and on-site energy generation have been suggested to balance energy generation and energy consumption, including installing PV solar cells on rooftops (Lützkendorf et al., 2015). However, due to the limited area of rooftops, solar PV modules seem unable to cover whole building energy demands, particularly for tall buildings (Freitas and Brito, 2019).

According to the Fraunhofer Institute, the price of PV solar cells reduced by more than seven times during 2008–2019. Furthermore, solar cell efficiency has improved significantly during recent years (ISE, 2019). Since 2020, solar energy is the cheapest renewable energy resource and less expensive than all fossil fuels. In response, countries around the world have sought to increase their solar energy generation to promote clean and sustainable environments. The UK and EU state's targets for their share of renewable energy consumption in 2020, 2030 and 2050 are 20%, 32% and 100%, respectively (Dowds and You, 2019). However, the UK did not meet the 2020 target, and if the UK and EU states hope to meet the 2030 and 2050 targets, their share of renewable energy generation needs to be increased dramatically, primarily through solar energy from solar farms and urban areas.

Whilst several methods have been developed for assessing the solar energy potential on rooftops, little attention has been paid to the potential of facades for solar energy generation (Freitas and Brito, 2019). The few studies into the solar potential of facades can be categorised into either raster- or vector-based methods. Raster-based and vector-based methods are used to analyse the solar energy on facades using Digital Surface Model and 2.5D model, respectively (Brito et al., 2019). In both categories, the rooftops were first extracted from LiDAR data. Then, based on the distance of rooftops to the ground, the facades are reconstructed. However, in this process, the facade structure and details are ignored. For example, the area below a balcony is unknown but is estimated as a facade. This estimation is error-prone and causes unreliability in the analysis. On the other hand, a vector-based 3D model provides the structure of the facade that helps determine the useful area of facades. However, there is still no vector-based 3D study. The goal of this study is to analyse the feasibility of installing PV modules on facades using vector-based 3D models, and ultimately to highlight the potential role of facades in the transition toward

* az431mos@gmail.com

† stephen.grebby@nottingham.ac.uk

zero-energy buildings.

2. Methodology

For the purpose of assessing the feasibility of BIPV on facades, a 3D model with Level of Detail (LoD) 2 is used for shadow effect analysis. The data were obtained from AccuCities as a free sample (AccuCities, 2021). For the assessment, a building (51.479170°N, -3.180060°E) was selected within Cardiff. The PV modules were arranged so as to cover the maximum possible area of rooftop and facades of the chosen building. The shadow effect and the total system losses were then estimated using Skelion v5.2.8, a plugin for Google Sketchup that allows the design of solar PV modules in a 3D Model. The shadow effect losses ($Shadow_{loss}$) are unique for each building, and are a function of the building shape and the surrounding neighbourhood. All PV modules with the $Shadow_{loss}$ greater than a 5% threshold were removed to minimise the losses. The facades are categorised in terms of the compass directions NE, NW, SE, SW and S according to their azimuth angle. The PV modules in Sketchup are illustrated in **Figure 1**, and the PV system specifications are shown in **Table 1**. The PV module model and system inverter model are "CanadianSolarCS6Pe-200" and "SMAAmericaSB3800TL-US-22[240V]", respectively.

Figure 1 The illustration PV modules in Sketchup2021.

Table 1 PV system specifications.

Section	Initial Number of Panels	Number of Panels considering threshold	Number of Inverters	Power (kWp)	Azimuth (°)	Tilt (°)	$Shadow_{loss}$ (%)	$Shadow_{loss}$ (%) with threshold
NW	166	166	7	33.2	318.91	90	0.14	0.14
SW	318	318	14	63.6	228.91	90	0.17	0.17
SE	108	63	3	12.6	138.91	90	5.23	1.42
S	39	10	1	2	168.04	90	17.2	1.21
NE	148	35	1	7	48.91	90	12.52	1.36
Roof	39	36	2	7.2	183	51	2.34	0.36

Meteorological information was obtained through NSRDB and PVGIS datasets. The PVGIS dataset contains several satellite-based estimations of solar irradiance databases such as CMSAF, SARA, and

COSMO (Amillo et al., 2014; Habte et al., 2017; Mueller et al., 2012).

The annual AC electricity production per kWh (AC_{ann}) on the rooftops of the building was calculated using Equation 1:

$$AC_{ann} = GTI \times e_{module} \times \left(1 - \frac{Shadow_{loss}}{100}\right) \quad (1)$$

where e_{module} is the module efficiency, which considers factors such as cell efficiency, array temperature, and the system components losses (ISE, 2019). The Global Tilted Irradiance (GTI) is the total solar irradiance received on a surface with defined tilt and azimuth (Brito et al., 2019). Several databases were used to compare the effect of solar irradiance datasets on the estimated GTI.

The annual income from PV solar energy for each building rooftop was calculated using Equation 2:

$$Income_{ann} = AC_{ann} \times EP \quad (2)$$

where EP is electricity price, which was set to £0.19 per kWh in 2021 for household usage in this study (UK Gov, 2021). The Payback Time (PBT) of a PV solar system is the required period to pay back the initial investment in PV solar system and can be calculated using:

$$PBT = \frac{Cost_{system}}{Income_{ann}} \quad (3)$$

where $Cost_{system}$ is the total system cost, which includes PV modules, inverters, system equipment, labour, engineering overhead and tax costs estimated by SAM software (Blair et al., 2014).

3. Results and Discussion

Estimates of GTI received on rooftop and facades using the CMFAS, SARAH, COSMO and NSRDB irradiance databases, are shown in **Figure 2**. As shown in **Figure 2**, the rooftop has the maximum estimated GTI, whereas the south-facing facades (SE, S, SW) receive much higher GTI than northward facing facades (NE and NW). It can be observed that the GTI estimations for all four databases are consistent, indicating that they will have negligible impacts on subsequent estimates of production and income.

Figure 2 Estimated GTI received by rooftop and facades.

The estimates for AC_{ann} , Yield, GTI, income, system cost, and PBT for the rooftop and facades are shown in **Table 2**. With PV modules usually have 25 years of lifetime, it would not be feasible in this instance to exploit the north-facing facades (NE and NW) since these have a PBT of more than 25 years. However, there is no significant difference in terms of the PBT between south-facing facades (SE, S and SW) and the rooftop. Given the increased area offered by facades and further decreases in PV cell cost, it is likely that it will become economically feasible to use facades alongside rooftops for increased PV solar energy generation in the near future.

Overall, the results of this study provide useful insights into the potential exploitation of facades for zero-energy building. However, further investigations into the feasibility are required, especially with the use of 3D models in which facade details such as windows can be considered. Furthermore, since BIPV can be embodied in walls and windows for different costs, a more detailed estimation for system cost to account for such differences is recommended. Nonetheless, the novel approach presented here,

of using 3D models to assess the solar energy potential, highlights the critical role that BIPV can play in achieving zero-energy building.

Table 2 Estimation of AC_{ann} , Yield, GTI, Income, system cost, and PBT

	AC_{ann} (kWh)	Yield (kWh/kWp)	GTI (kWh/m ² /year)	Income (£/year)	System Cost (£)	PBT (Year)
NW	10,676.54	321.58	429.10	2,028.54	67,832.53	33.43
SW	45,527.84	715.85	866.77	8,650.29	127,684.74	14.76
SE	9,075.82	720.30	879.34	1,724.40	23,940.89	13.88
S	1,533.88	766.94	931.61	291.43	3,990.15	13.69
NE	2,401.54	343.08	456.49	456.29	12,970.44	28.42
Roof	7,653.22	1,062.95	1260.21	1,454.11	14,902.54	10.24

References

- AccuCities, 2021. 3D Cardiff City Model Sample. URL accucities.com/product/free-3d-cardiff-city-model-sample/
- Amillo, A.G., Huld, T., Müller, R., 2014. A new database of global and direct solar radiation using the eastern meteosat satellite, models and validation. *Remote Sens.* 6, 8165–8189.
- Blair, N., Dobos, A.P., Freeman, J., Neises, T., Wagner, M., Ferguson, T., Gilman, P., Janzou, S., 2014. System advisor model, sam 2014.1. 14: General description. NREL.
- Brito, M.C., Redweik, P., Catita, C., Freitas, S., Santos, M., 2019. 3D solar potential in the urban environment: A case study in lisbon. *Energies* 12, 3457.
- Dowds, M., You, S., 2019. Economic analysis of the routes for fulfilment of net-zero energy buildings (NZEBS) in the UK. *Energy Procedia* 158, 3541–3546.
- Freitas, S., Brito, M.C., 2019. Solar façades for future cities. *Renew. Energy Focus* 31, 73–79.
- Habte, A., Sengupta, M., Lopez, A., 2017. Evaluation of the national solar radiation database (NSRDB): 1998-2015. NREL.
- ISE, 2019. Photovoltaic Report.
- Lützkendorf, T., Foliente, G., Balouktsi, M., Wiberg, A.H., 2015. Net-zero buildings: incorporating embodied impacts. *Build. Res. Inf.* 43, 62–81.
- Mueller, R., Behrendt, T., Hammer, A., Kemper, A., 2012. A new algorithm for the satellite-based retrieval of solar surface irradiance in spectral bands. *Remote Sens.* 4, 622–647.
- UK Gov, 2021. Average annual domestic electricity bills by home and non-home supplier (QEP 2.2.1).

Biographies

Mostafa Azizkhani has an MS.c in GIS. He has been working and conducting research in the field of solar energy potential mapping on large and small scales using GIS tools and methods for more than 7 years.

Stephen Grebby is an Assistant Professor in Earth Observation at the University of Nottingham's Nottingham Geospatial Institute. He has over 13 years of experience in the development of innovative remote sensing and GIS techniques to geoscience and energy-related applications.